

www.arseam.com

International Journal of
Advances in Engineering
& Scientific Research

Academic Research
IN SCIENCE, ENGINEERING, ART & MANAGEMENT

International Journal
of Advances in
Engineering &
Scientific Research
(IJAESR)

ISSN: 2349 -3607 (Online)
ISSN: 2349 -4824 (Print)

Available online at:
<http://www.arseam.com/content/volume-1-issue-4-aug-2014>

Email: editor@arseam.com

Instructions for authors and
subscription information:
<http://www.arseam.com/>

IMPROVING WEB INFORMATION QUALITY BY AGE DETECTION & SECURITY ANALYSIS OF WEB PAGES

Limna Das P^{#1}, Sanjeetha.R^{#2}

*#Department of Computer Science and Engineering, M.S .Ramaiah Institute of Technology
Bangalore, Karnataka, India*

Abstract

The Web is evolving very rapidly due to the ease of publishing information. At the same time, the Web is vulnerable to time passage as much new content is created continuously and old content becomes quickly obsolete. It is thus important to distinguish fresh and obsolete content in Web pages. Many web pages contain elements inserted at different time points. Some pages show timestamps or other temporal metadata informing about the creation dates of content elements. The main function of temporal metadata is to inform users about the age of page content. Readers often implicitly utilize this information to better understand the content by correctly locating it on a time scale. It is especially evident in the case of time-sensitive documents. In practice, however, pages often do not offer any clues about the age of their content. The reader has to optimistically think the web page is latest and proceed. In other cases, temporal annotations provided by page authors may sometimes be misleading and should not always be trusted. The web pages that are visited may not be secure as they may contain malicious contents like viruses, worms, spyware, key loggers etc. There has to be some means to find out the security of the web page before using it. In our project, we describe a novel concept for detecting approximate creation dates of content elements in Web pages and measure the security level of the web page visited. To detect the age of a web page we dynamically reconstruct page histories using data extracted from external sources such as Web archives and efficiently search inside them to detect insertion dates of content elements. To measure the security of the web page we check certain security attributes like Security risks, Remote access software, Adware, Spyware, Dialers, Malicious downloads, Drive by downloads, Suspicious browser changes, Phishing attacks, Information stealers, Trojans and Suspicious applications with the help of Security websites that are designed to help users discern safe Web sites from unsafe ones.

Keywords—Web Information Quality, trustworthiness of Information on the Web, quality factors, web Archives, Information age, Information Security.

I. INTRODUCTION

In our project, we describe a novel concept for detecting approximate creation dates of content elements in Web pages and measure the security level of the web page visited. To detect the age of a web page we dynamically reconstruct page histories using data extracted from external sources such as Web archives and efficiently search inside them to detect insertion dates of content elements. To measure the security of the web page we check certain security attributes. The objective of this project is to provide a method for automatic generation of temporal metadata by determining the age of content elements in pages. Our proposal is based on searching inside page histories to discover the creation dates of page elements. The creation date of content is estimated as the most probable time point of its insertion into the page that can be estimated from past data. This is done by automatically selecting and downloading past snapshots of pages from existing Web archival repositories.

The next area of concern is security of web pages. The web pages that are visited may not be secure as they may contain malicious contents like viruses, worms, spyware, key loggers etc. To measure the security of the web page we check certain security attributes like Security risks, Remote access software, Adware, Spyware, Dialers, Malicious downloads, Drive by downloads, Suspicious browser changes, Phishing attacks, Information stealers, Trojans and Suspicious applications with the help of Security websites that are designed to help users discern safe Web sites from unsafe ones. After analyzing these factors we provide a rating which indicates whether the visited web page is secure or not.

II. RELATED WORK

A Web Portal Data Quality Model (PDQM): PDQM is a data quality model for Web portals which focuses upon the data consumer perspective.

Fig 1 Basis for the construction of PDQM

As shown in Fig 1, its definition is based on three key aspects: Web DQ attributes, the Data consumer perspective, and the Web portal’s functionalities.

Fig 2 The development process of PDQM.

First step was to consider that many DQ attributes can be found in literature which could be used to evaluate the DQ in Web portals. Concretely, this idea was to take advantage of previous work applied

to the Web and extend it to Web portals. Secondly, it has taken into account the fact that DQ cannot be assessed independently from the users who use data, which is suggested by most of the authors who define the Data Quality concept as “fitness for use”. The DQ expectations of data consumers on the Internet are grouped into six categories: Privacy, Commitment, Quality of Values, Improvement Presentation, and Content.

Thirdly, assume that data consumers judge DQ when using the functionalities provided by a Web portal. Thus, if we know the main functionalities of a Web portal these can guide us towards identifying which aspects of DQ are more important for data consumers when they assess the DQ. Some basic functions are as follows: Administration, Data Points, , Security, Help Features, Integration, Content Management, Process and Action, Collaboration and Communication, Search Capabilities, Personalization, Presentation, Taxonomy.

The PDQM was divided into two parts considering these three essential aspects. In the first part we defined the theoretical version of our model, PDQM(t). The main goal of this part was to obtain a set of DQ attributes that can be used to evaluate the DQ in Web portals from the data consumers’ perspective.

The second part consisted of the transformation of PDQM(t) into an operational model. The main goal of this part was to define a structure through which to organize DQ attributes by associating measures and criteria with them.

III. SEARCHING METHODS FOR AGE DETECTION

Detecting content creation dates is done by a search for the oldest snapshots containing content elements that occur in the present page version. In order to detect the creation date of an element, it is necessary to find a pair of consecutive snapshots, in which only the newer one contains the element. Suppose that there are n snapshots $s_1, s_2 \dots s_n$ with respective timestamps $t_1, t_2 \dots t_n$. s_n is the snapshot of the present page version.

Definition

Time point tk is considered to be the creation date of an element of s_n if the element is contained in snapshot s_k whose timestamp is tk , while not being contained in snapshot s_{k-1} whose time stamp is $tk-1$ and $tk-1 < tk$.

Change detection has to be thus done between the selected past snapshots and the present page version in order to find creation dates of content elements. The algorithm then examines if there are any lines with the same content in the compared documents using *diff* method, which is based on finding longest matching subsequences.

A. Sequential Search

The naïve approach is to sequentially download snapshots from the resource list starting from the youngest one. Each snapshot is then compared with the present page version until all the content elements will have their creation dates detected. This is often the case when the elements in the current page version are old and repositories store many past snapshots of the page. This search is often impractical as it means downloading and comparing large number of snapshots.

Fig 3. Sequential search for one content element represented by a yellow dot (t_{ns} is the element's creation date; t_n is the present time).

B. Discussion

There will be usually a certain error involved with the age detection process as demonstrated in Fig4. The search process finds the oldest page snapshot that contains the element. Let us denote its timestamp by t_k . However, the actual time point of the element's insertion is somewhere between t_{k-1} and t_k , where t_{k-1} denotes the youngest page snapshot that does not contain that element.

Fig4. Error of creation date detection due to fragmentary data.

Let us suppose that the actual history of the page is depicted in the bottom timeline in Fig4. In order to decrease the maximum possible error, the middle point of $\langle t_{k-1}, t_k \rangle$ could be considered as the element's creation date. However, assuming t_k to be the creation date is a safer choice as it provides the assurance that the actual age of the element is not smaller than the length of the period $\langle t_k, t_n \rangle$.

C. Inverse sequential search

For improving search efficiency and speed of calculation an inverse sequential search can be used. It acts in the reverse order of sequential search. First, it looks for the oldest snapshot which contains any element that also occurs in the current page version instead of the youngest snapshot as in the previous method. Inverse searching differs from a usual binary search done on an ordered sequence in two aspects.

The proposed search method can thus result in considerable cost savings in case of pages with many past snapshots and relatively old content when compared to the previous method.

IV. INFORMATION SECURITY

As direct access to the source may not be (should not be!) possible. Indirect measures like evaluating the technical infrastructure used with respect to known vulnerabilities can be used to access how secure the data source is. Possible candidates are:

- the operating system (version, patch level)
- web server/application server (version)
- database
- Application server technology (not a really appropriate term. I mean whether the website is a PHP, RoR, JSP, etc site)
- Hosting type

- open ports

The communication protocol can also be a measure: encrypted communication over plain text protocols, for example (HTTPS, SSL versus HTTP). History of attacks and the degree of success based on a neutral, third-party source of information can also be factored in.

Front-end security can be evaluated based on:

- the operation system
- browser
- Scripting and active controls used (JavaScript, ActiveX, Flash), etc used.

A. Measurement Techniques

- Maintain a list of measures
- Maintain (and update) the rate of each measure
 - <http://nvd.nist.gov/>,
 - <http://web.nvd.nist.gov/view/vuln/search> -US National Vulnerability Database
 - <http://osvdb.org/> - Open source vulnerability database
 - <https://www.kb.cert.org/vuls/> - US-CERT Vulnerability Notes Database
 - <http://vdb.dragonsoft.com/> - One more vulnerability database
- Fetch information, compare with the rating maintained and supply rating
 - <http://uptime.netcraft.com> can be used to get the server's information
 - <http://whois.net>
 - <http://www.wolframalpha.com/>

Fig 5. Resultant output for Age Interpreter

Fig 6. Resultant output for Age Interpreter as XML format

Fig 7. Resultant output for Security Interpreter as XML format

V. CONCLUSIONS

Web pages often contain elements created at arbitrary time points. However, usually, it is difficult to know their creation dates. In this project, we have proposed a method for automatic discovery of the creation dates of page content. This is a retrospective approach that utilizes past snapshots of pages obtained from external, archival repositories in order to dynamically reconstruct page histories at user's request. The histories are then efficiently searched for time points when content elements were observed for the first time. In result, it is possible to assign approximate creation dates to page content. Web pages are not secure they may contain Security risks, Remote access software, Adware, Spyware, Dialers, Malicious downloads, Drive by downloads, Suspicious browser changes, Phishing attacks, Information stealers, Trojans and Suspicious applications. In this project we are successful

in checking the web page to detect the presence of any such factors and providing a rating for its security. Using this rating the users can decide whether to trust the site or not.

REFERENCES

- [1] www.archive.org
- [2] Adam Jatowt, Yukiko Kawai, Katsumi Tanaka, *Detecting age of page content*, Proceedings of the 9th annual ACM international workshop on Web information and data management, Lisbon, Portugal, November 9, 2007,
- [3] *Quality-Based Information Filtering in the Context of Web-Based Systems*, Christian Bizer, 2007
- [4] John Beckford. *Quality - A Critical Introduction*. Routledge, London, 2nd edition, 2001.
- [5] Joseph Juran. *The Quality Control Handbook*. McGraw-Hill, New York, 3rd edition, 1974.